

Preparation of Active Esters of a Carboxylic Acid and some *N*-protected Amino Acids

REDA A. KABLI, SYED A. RAHMAN and ABDULLAH B. EL-TAHIR

Department of Chemistry, King Abd laziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

Manuscript received 22 August 1984, accepted 11 September 1985

Carboxylates¹ react rapidly and smoothly with 3-unsubstituted isoxazolium salts under very mild conditions to yield enol esters. In this paper we report some reactions of *N*-ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*) isoxazolium cation with acetate ion and some nitrogen blocked amino acids to give enol esters. These reactions exemplify a process for converting a carboxylate group into a reactive ester group by a very rapid and smooth reaction occurring under conditions of exceptional mildness.

WOODWARD² showed that carboxylic acids (*i.e.* HOOC-CHR-NHZ) react rapidly and smoothly with *N*-ethylisoxazolium salts under very mild conditions to yield activated enol esters. The latter undergoes a facile reaction with amino groups as in amino acids, affording the peptide in high yield.

With reference to these reactions, the initial step in the coupling process was postulated³ to proceed *via* ketoketenimine formed by ring opening of the ylide. The ketenimine was directly observed and its existence was subsequently confirmed by isolation⁴. Attack by the carboxylate species proceeds across the reactive cumulative system producing the intermediate which transacylates to the active ester. The use of benzisoxazolium salt was also reported⁵ to yield active esters presumably through the same general pathway.

Experimental

Reaction of N-ethylnaphth(1,2-d)isoxazolium fluoborate with acetate ion. 2-Acetyl-N-ethylnaphthamide: A solution of sodium acetate in water was brought to pH 5.5 by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid and stirred as *N*-ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium fluoborate was slowly added as fine powder. Within minutes, a white crystalline solid separated. After a while the crystals were filtered off, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from dichloromethane (Found: C, 69.85; H, 5.84; N, 5.48. C₁₅H₁₅NO₅ calcd. C, 70.0; H, 5.8; N, 5.4%).

The infrared spectrum revealed two strong carbonyl absorptions at 1766 and 1650 cm⁻¹. The rather high frequency band satisfied the requirement for C=O in ester owing to the naphthyl ring conjugation with alcohol oxygen, and the low frequency band was assigned to C=O (amide I band) of amide group. The reduced frequency in this case is attributed to the resonance effect. Another conspicuous feature of the infrared spectrum is the rather strong absorption at 3300 cm⁻¹ due to N-H stretching, together with the presence of a large broad band at

1200 cm⁻¹ associated with C-O-C stretching in ester. Finally, the N-H bending and C-N stretching bands occur at 1640 and 1400 cm⁻¹, respectively. The nmr spectrum (chloroform-*d*) provides exhaustive confirmation for the structure of the compound. Particularly noteworthy feature was the methylene resonance of *N*-ethyl group, which appeared as a quintet at δ 3.6. The splitting was produced by adjacent methyl and N-H protons. A triplet of the three protons at δ 1.3 represented methyl group and the intense sharp singlet of three protons at 2.3 represented methyl group of the ester. The nmr spectrum further showed a broad flat absorption centered at δ 6.0, typical of N-H absorption. Finally, a downfield multiplet at δ 7.6 was assigned to six naphthalene protons.

Reaction of N-ethylnaphth(1,2-d)isoxazolium fluoborate with N-phthaloylglycine. 2-o-Phthaloylglycyl-1-N-ethylnaphthamide: *N*-Ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium fluoborate (1 mol) in acetonitrile was added to the solution of *N*-phthaloylglycine (1 mol) containing triethylamine (1 mol) in the same solvent. The mixture was stirred at room temperature till the reagents dissolved completely. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue obtained was recrystallised from acetonitrile (85%), m.p. 180-182° (Found: C, 68.6; H, 4.45; N, 6.92. C₂₅H₁₈N₂O₅ calcd. C, 68.65; H, 4.47; N, 6.96%).

The ir and nmr spectra provided exhaustive confirmation for the structure. The ir spectrum showed a strong broad absorption at 3400 cm⁻¹ attributable to N-H stretching. A combination of a strong broad absorption centered at 1735 cm⁻¹ for C=O band, and a typical broad strong C-O band at 1220 cm⁻¹ was the evidence for an ester group. Two strong bands in the carbonyl region at 1750 and 1770 cm⁻¹ were indicative of the presence of C=O group associated with phthalyl group. Finally, a strong absorption at 1640 cm⁻¹ satisfied the requirement of N-H bending (amide II band). The nmr spectra showed an upfield signal centered at δ 1.4 due to N-CH₂-CH₃ group and the two N-CH₂-

CH₂ appeared as quintet at 3.7 splitted by N-H and methyl protons. The N-H proton signal at δ 5.9 was severely broadened by the quadruple integration with nitrogen. The strongly deshielded position of methylene absorption as strong sharp singlet at δ 4.8, placed it on carbonyl function of the OOC-CH₂-N group of *N*-phthaloylglycine moiety. The multiplets at δ 7.4 and 7.9 integrating to ten protons are ascribed to benzene and naphthalene rings, respectively.

Reaction of *N*-ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium fluoborate with *N*-phthaloylalanine. 2-*o*-Phthaloylalanine-1-*N*-ethylnaphthamide: A solution of *N*-ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium fluoborate in acetonitrile was treated with a solution of *N*-phthaloylalanine (1 mol) in the same solvent containing one equivalent triethylamine. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0° until the reagents dissolved, then left to stand overnight. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure, the resulting gummy residue on scratching with glass rod gave a white precipitate. The solid so obtained, was recrystallised from ethanol-water (80%), m.p 175° (Found: C, 68.95; H, 5.0; N, 6.65. C₂₄H₂₀N₂O₅ calcd. C, 69.2; H, 4.8; N, 6.7%).

The infrared spectrum was in accord with the proposed structure of the compound. It consisted of four prominent bands in the region of 1640 to 1780 cm⁻¹, due to strong carbonyl absorptions. The broad band at 1640 cm⁻¹ was assigned to amide (I) band, the band at 1720 cm⁻¹ was ascribed to C=O group in ester, and the remaining two typically broad absorptions at 1770 and 1780 cm⁻¹ were attributed to carbonyl function of the phthaloyl group. Finally, the broad band centered at 3400 and 1590 cm⁻¹ corresponded to N-H stretching and amide (II) band. The nmr spectrum was also quite consistent with the structure of the compound. It showed an upfield triplet at δ 1.25 due to CONH-CH₂-CH₃ of the amide group and a downfield quintet at δ 3.7 due to CONH-CH₂-CH₃. The N-H proton showed a typical broad absorption at δ 6.2. The upfield 3-proton doublet represented the COO-CH(CH₃)-N absorption. The strongly deshielded position of the -CH- absorption at δ 5.3 confirmed its proximity with carbonyl group. The integrator showed the multiplet centered at about δ 7.4 and 7.9 due to the naphthalene and benzene protons and contained ten protons.

Reaction of *N*-ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium fluoborate with *N*-benzyloxycarbonylserine. 2-*o*-Benzyloxycarbonylseryl-1-*N*-ethylnaphthamide: A solution of benzyloxycarbonylserine (1 mol) and triethylamine in acetonitrile was added to a cold solution (0°) of *N*-ethylnaphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium fluoborate in the same solvent. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then concentrated to a solid residue which was recrystallised from acetonitrile to give the title compound (78%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 66.32; H, 5.7; N, 6.36. CHNO calcd. C, 66.05; H, 5.50; N, 6.42%).

The infrared spectrum of the title compound revealed two strong carbonyl absorptions at 1760

and 1690 cm⁻¹ attributable to C=O group of ester and C=O (amide I band) of amide group. A broad band at 3300 to 3500 cm⁻¹ overlapping a band at 3350 cm⁻¹ spelt out hydroxyl and N-H groups, respectively. The nmr spectrum revealed a triplet and a quintet at δ 1.2 and 3.5 due to methyl and methylene protons, respectively of the *N*-ethyl group. The splitting of methylene protons has been produced by neighbouring methyl and N-H protons. The large singlet centring at δ 5.1 must result from the methylene group on benzyloxycarbonyl group. A triplet and a doublet at δ 6.15 and 5.8 are assigned to the methine and hydroxymethylene group of *N*-blocked serine moiety, respectively.

Discussion

With reference to Scheme 1 the initial step between the naphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium cation and acetate ion leads to the intermediate naphthoketoketenimine (1). Attack by the acetate ion proceeds across the reactive cumulative system producing iminoanhydride (2) which transacylates to the active ester, namely 2-acetyl-*N*-ethylnaphthamide (3). The formation of active esters of amino acids (Scheme 2)

2-*o*-Acetyl-*N*-ethylnaphthamide

Scheme 1

Active ester of *N*-protected amino acids
Glycine: R=H; X=Phthaloyl
Alanine: R=CH₃; X=Phthaloyl
Serine: R=CH₂OH; X=Benzyloxycarbonyl

Scheme 2

from *N*-ethyl-naphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium cation likewise be rationalised as proceeding from an iminoanhydride (4) which transacylates to the active ester (5).

The fact that *N*-ethyl-naphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium cation reacts with extraordinary facility and ease with acetate ion to give enol ester encouraged us to apply this reaction for converting *N*-blocked amino acids into reactive esters (5). The active esters of *N*-protected amino acids are known to undergo a facile reaction with amino group of amino acids affording the coupled peptide⁶.

We now find that *N*-ethyl-naphth(1,2-*d*)isoxazolium cation reacts with a variety of *N*-protected amino acids to give a crystalline active esters in a good yield. Even benzyloxycarbonylserine gives a crystalline active ester in 78% yield. The great difficulty in making active ester of benzyloxycarbonylserine has been commented upon by Bodanszky and Ondetti⁷. The success in the present instance

evidently depends on the fact that the crucial reaction involves an intra-molecular nucleophilic displacement by a naphthol rather than an inter-molecular one as in those cases involving the use of dicyclohexylcarbodiimide.

References

1. R. B. WOODWARD and R. A. OLOFSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1007.
2. R. B. WOODWARD and R. A. OLOFSON, 'Tetrahedron Supplement', No. 7, 1966, p. 415.
3. R. B. WOODWARD, R. A. OLOFSON and H. MAYER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1010.
4. R. B. WOODWARD and D. J. WOODMANN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2098.
5. D. S. KEMP and R. B. WOODWARD, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 8019.
6. Specialist Periodical Reports, "Amino acids, Peptides and Proteins", Chemical Society, London, 1968-1976, Vols. 1-8.
7. M. BODANSZKY and M. A. ONDETTI, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1966, 26.